

ETHNOPSYCHOLOGY IS DEFINITION, HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE, SUBJECT OF STUDY, METHODS

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Annotation: *Ethnopsychology is a developing science that studies the relationship between culture and the human psyche. This industry is in the process of formation, and therefore its exact definition is not yet available. In the article we will learn about how this scientific direction developed, what is the subject and method of its study.*

Key words: *madaniyat, urf-odat, e'tiqod, dunyoqarash, tafakkur, Xitoy, Rim, Arab, marosim.*

Most specialists involved in the study of modern ethnopsychology do not consider it an independent discipline. This scientific branch borders on two fundamental areas - psychology and culture. At the same time, ethnopsychology studies the problems of more than two areas. It is no coincidence that scientists use different terms to designate this discipline, which is largely due to the content in ethnopsychology of the topics and methods of research in psychology, sociology, cultural studies, history, and anthropology. Translated from Greek, ethnos means "people", psyche is "soul", and logos is a word, knowledge, teaching.

Ethnopsychology is a scientific research direction:

- national features of emotional-volitional and mental cognitive processes, reactions characteristic of representatives of certain nationalities;
- states and personality traits of representatives of various ethnic minorities;
- originality of phenomena and processes in the socio-psychological sphere of individual nations and peoples;
- issues of national identity, ethnohistorical values and orientation;
- characteristics of the culture of certain ethnic groups.

Speaking of ethnopsychology as a complex scientific study, during which ethnic, cultural, psychological characteristics of people and entire nations are considered, it is easy to single out its object. They are entire ethnic groups, nations, peoples, ethnic and national minorities. The subject of ethnopsychology is the self-consciousness of people belonging to a certain socio-ethnic community, their understanding of their own interests and understanding of the true position of the nation in the system of social relations, the specifics of interactions with other ethnic groups.

Ethnopsychology as a science has specific goals and objectives. First of all, this scientific direction helps to carry out a comprehensive analysis and summarize information about the influencing factors and sources of the formation of specific nationalities, create psychological portraits of representatives of various ethnic communities and, on their basis, identify socio-political, economic, historical and cultural prerequisites for further development. In addition, the subject of ethnopsychology is the specificity of the motivational component of the psyche of people belonging to a particular nation, which allows us to study in detail such qualities as, for example, efficiency, initiative, degree of diligence, etc., which determine important indicators of productive activity and behavioral features.

Ethnopsychology is a science in which studies of differentiated indicators of mental activity of people belonging to a particular nationality are carried out. The works of scientists in this field make it possible to reveal the degree of adherence to logic, the speed of thought processes and the depth of abstraction, perception, completeness and efficiency of associations, imagination, concentration and stability of attention. Thanks to ethnopsychology, one can draw a conclusion about the features of the psycho-emotional background, the dynamics of the manifestation of feelings of representatives of a certain nationality, their emotional behavior.

One of the tasks of ethnopsychology is to identify problems in the communicative environment that arise due to differences in the national mental makeup of people and forms of interaction. Based on the results of research work, a conclusion is made about the degree of influence of communication and relationships on the nature

of the ongoing socio-psychological processes in groups, their hierarchical structure, traditions, and norms of behavior. In addition, ethnopsychology creates the necessary ground for predicting various social processes in certain regions of the country or in other states.

Studying the mentality of people of a particular nation or nationality, scientists use various scientific tools. The most common method of ethnopsychology is observation. It is applied in natural conditions. The method of conscious vision must be purposeful and applied systematically. This tool will be effective only in the case of non-intervention of the observer, whose task is to study the external manifestations of the psyche of people belonging to specific ethnic groups. The disadvantage of this method is the subjectivity of the conclusion of a specialist. The method of covert surveillance with the help of audio or video devices is recognized as very effective in ethnopsychology.

The second way of research is experiment. It includes all ascertaining methods. The experiment is used as a tool for active exploration. If the method of observation presupposes the non-intervention of the researcher, then in this case the experimenter himself must organize the whole process and take care of creating the necessary conditions for the experiment. As a rule, studies are carried out with representatives of different ethnic groups, but in the same conditions. The experiment can be laboratory and natural (the second option is more common).

The method of testing and questioning in ethnopsychology allows you to determine the personality traits of the subject or draw a conclusion about the features of the national character, hierarchy of motives, temperament. The disadvantage of questionnaire tests is often the unreliability of their results. In comparison with this method of research, the survey method does not imply the identification of the respondent, which allows you to get a higher percentage of truthful information. In addition, an oral survey is much faster than a written test or questionnaire.

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